

Supplementary Material S1:

Mathematical Details of the Robust Seasonal Trend Analysis (RSTA)

S1. Modelling Seasonal Parameters Using Harmonic Regression

In the first stage of the original seasonal trend analysis (STA), a harmonic regression model is fitted to each annual time series as a function of Julian date (Eastman et al., 2009). Unlike traditional Fourier-based approaches, harmonic regression explicitly accounts for the exact calendar dates of the observations, allowing seasonality to be modelled in continuous time and producing more reliable results when observations are not perfectly regularly spaced (Roerink et al., 2000, 2003). In this sense, two frequencies are used to capture the dominant seasonal components in the data while avoiding high-frequency noise (Equation S1).

$$y = \alpha_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{n=2} \left\{ a_n \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nt}{T}\right) + b_n \cos\left(\frac{2\pi nt}{T}\right) \right\} + e \quad (\text{S1})$$

where:

α_0 is the intercept (mean level) of the series; a_n and b_n : these are the coefficients of the sinusoidal and cosinusoidal terms, respectively; n is a harmonic (an integer multiple of the fundamental frequency). Harmonics allow the series to be decomposed into components of different frequencies. In this formula, n ranges from 1 to 2, meaning that the first two harmonics are being considered; t : represents time; T : represents the length of the period; e represents the error term.

After solving the harmonic regression and rearranging the terms, ignoring the error term, the generalised seasonal curve can be expressed as (Equation S2):

$$y = \alpha_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{n=2} \alpha_n \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nt}{T} + \varphi_n\right) \quad (\text{S2})$$

where:

α_n are the amplitudes for each harmonic, indicating the strength of the annual and semi-annual cycles; φ_n is the phase shift (ranging from 0° to 360°) for each harmonic, determining the timing of the peaks and troughs of the cycles.

Each annual dataset undergoes harmonic regression to calculate the seasonality parameters (amplitudes and phases) at the pixel level (Eastman and Clark Labs, 2024). In practice, the most informative seasonality parameter is amplitude 0, that is, the baseline level or annual mean of the series (Eastman and Clark Labs, 2025; Gutiérrez-Hernández and García, 2024).

S2. Spatiotemporal Trend Analysis

S2.1. Serial Correlation Control

Before the second stage, we introduced an additional preprocessing step to improve Type I error control in the subsequent trend testing, which is not part of the original STA framework. In STA (Eastman et al., 2009), trend analyses are applied independently to each seasonality parameter, originally using the Theil–Sen slope estimator and, in later implementations, also incorporating the Mann–Kendall test (Eastman et al., 2013). However, the underlying issue remains the same: when trend testing is applied to time series with serial autocorrelation, the assumption of independence among observations is violated, leading to temporal correlation among successive values (Hamed and Ramachandra Rao, 1998; Patakamuri and O’Brien N, 2021). As a result, these persistent correlations can be mistakenly interpreted as a significant monotonic trend, leading to an inflation of Type I errors. The proposed preprocessing step reduces this risk by excluding unreliable time series before trend testing, thereby limiting false-positive detections (Fuenzalida and Rosenblüth, 1990).

Prewhitening refers to the removal of serial correlation in the error (noise) component of a series (Kulkarni and von Storch, 1995; von Storch, 1999). The term “whiten” is used because this process aims to make the series behave like white noise, with independent values and a constant mean. The prefix “pre” indicates that this is a preliminary step undertaken before applying other statistical analyses that assume the data are white noise or lack serial correlation. Yue and Wang (2002) criticised the original prewhitening procedure for making it more likely to accept the null hypothesis of no trend. To

overcome this, we used an iterative trend-free prewhitening (TFPW) procedure following Wang and Swail (2001), which effectively addresses this issue.

The Wang and Swail (2001) iterative TFPW procedure eliminates first-order serial correlation in time-series data using a multi-stage prewhitening technique. The procedure carried out here assumes that the time series Y_t can be described as (Equation S3):

$$Y_t = a + bt + X_t \quad (\text{S3})$$

where X_t is a lag-1 red noise process, meaning it is a time-dependent process influenced by its previous value (Equation S4):

$$X_t = \rho X_{t-1} + e_t \quad (\text{S4})$$

and:

a is the intercept, representing the baseline level of the series; b is the trend slope, indicating the rate of change over time; t is time; X_{t-1} is the value of the red noise process at the previous time point; ρ is the serial correlation, indicating the strength of the relationship between consecutive terms in the series; and e_t is the white noise error term, which is a random variable with a mean of zero and constant variance, and it is uncorrelated with past values.

The procedure described by Wang and Swail (2001) to remove the red noise component yields a new series (W_t) that can be described as (Equation S5):

$$W_t = a' + bt + e'_t \quad (\text{S5})$$

where a' is the adjusted intercept calculated as (Equation S6):

$$a' = \frac{a + \rho b}{1 - \rho} \quad (\text{S6})$$

And e'_t is the transformed white noise error term calculated as (Equation S7):

$$e'_t = \frac{e_t}{1-\rho} \quad (S7)$$

An iterative procedure is used to estimate the true serial correlation (ρ) and the trend-preserving pre-whitened series is calculated as (Equation S8):

$$W_t = \frac{Y_t - \rho Y_{t-1}}{1-\rho} \quad (S8)$$

This procedure corrects for serial correlation in pixels that show significant autocorrelation at the 95% confidence level using the Durbin–Watson test. Equation (S9) for the Durbin–Watson statistic (d) is (Durbin and Watson, 1950, 1951):

$$d = \frac{\sum_{t=2}^T (e_t - e_{t-1})^2}{\sum_{t=1}^T e_t^2} \quad (S9)$$

where:

T is the total number of observations (i.e., the final time point in the time series); t is the specific time index within the series, ranging from 1 to T ; and e_t is the residual value at time t , representing the difference between the observed and predicted values at that specific time point.

The Durbin–Watson statistic ranges from 0 to 4. A value of 2 indicates no serial autocorrelation. If the statistic is less than 2, it indicates the presence of a positive serial correlation. Conversely, if the statistic is greater than 2, it indicates negative serial autocorrelation.

Finally, the TFPW-corrected series retains the same trend as the original while removing serial correlation. Typically, the pre-whitening process reduces the sample size by one, as there is no prior value for the first observation. In ETM (Eastman and Clark Labs, 2020), however, the Prais–Winsten transformation is used to estimate the value for the first date, allowing the entire dataset to be maintained (Kmenta, 2004; Prais and Winsten, 1954).

S2.2. Spatially Contextualised Trend Testing

In the second stage, a Theil-Sen (TS) median trend analysis is applied to the five shape parameters over the entire series duration (Sen, 1968; Theil, 1950). This method, which can handle data with up to 29% outliers, focuses on long-term trends while rejecting short-term variability and noise. We also applied the contextual Mann–Kendall (CMK) test to assess the significance of the seasonal trend analysis results (Neeti and Eastman, 2011). Unlike the original Mann–Kendall test (Kendall, 1975; Mann, 1945), the CMK test uses contextual information (first-order eight neighbours) to correct for spatial correlation while also addressing cross-correlation.

The TS slope estimator calculates the median slope from all possible pairwise comparisons of observation values, resulting in a total of N slopes, where $N = \frac{n(n-1)}{2}$. This non-parametric technique for estimating the magnitude of trends in time series data was introduced by Theil (1950) and later refined by Sen (1968). The equations used to estimate the TS slope and intercept are given as follows (Equation S10):

$$\text{TS slope} = \text{median} \left(\frac{X_j - X_i}{t_j - t_i} \right) \quad (\text{S10})$$

$$\text{Intercept} = X_i - \text{medianSlope} * t_i, \quad \text{for } i = 1 \dots n$$

where:

$X_j - X_i$ is the difference in the observation values between two points in time; $t_j - t_i$ is the difference in time between two observations, with t_j being later than t_i ; and, here, N represents the total number of non-zero differences $t_j - t_i$ for all pairs (i, j) such that $1 \leq i < j \leq n$. i and j are indices that iterate through the data series, ensuring that i is always less than j , so that all possible pairs of observations are considered without repetition or reversing the order. This is necessary to calculate the slope differences between each pair of observations in the TS method.

This approach offers several advantages. The TS technique is robust to outliers, enabling it to ignore extreme values without affecting the overall slope estimation. It can reject up to approximately 29% of the sample size as outliers (known as the breakdown bound: $1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 29.3\%$) without compromising the results, as described by Hoaglin et al. (2000).

A widely used method is the MK test to assess the significance of the TS slope (Kendall, 1975; Mann, 1945). Like the TS approach, the MK test evaluates the slopes between all possible pairs of data points. In the MK test, the data are ordered chronologically, with each data point serving as a reference for the subsequent data points in time. The statistic S , introduced by Kendall (1975) is defined as follows (Equation S11):

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \text{sign}(x_i - x_j) \quad (\text{S11})$$

where:

$$\text{sign}(x_j - x_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x_j - x_i > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x_j - x_i = 0 \\ -1 & \text{if } x_j - x_i < 0 \end{cases}$$

and:

S is the MK test statistic that sums the signs of all differences between pairs of observations; n represents the number of observations in the time series; x_i and x_j are the values of the time series at time points i and j , respectively. In the MK test, the sign function is used to evaluate whether the difference between two values in a time series is positive, negative, or zero.

The variance σ^2 of S is used to normalise the statistic and is calculated as (Equation S12):

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5)}{18} - \sum_{t=1}^g \frac{t(t-1)(2t+5)}{18} \quad (\text{S12})$$

where:

σ^2 is the variance of the statistic S ; g is the number of tied groups in the data set; t represents the size of each tied group. The first term ($\sigma^2 = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5)}{18}$) accounts for the total variance, while the second term ($\sum_{t=1}^g \frac{t(t-1)(2t+5)}{18}$) corrects for ties in the data.

The Z statistic is used to determine the significance of the trend (Equation S13):

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{\sigma} & \text{if } S > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } S = 0 \\ \frac{S+1}{\sigma} & \text{if } S < 0 \end{cases} \quad (\text{S13})$$

And (Equation S14):

$$p = 2 \times \Phi(-|Z|) \quad (\text{S14})$$

where:

Z is the standardised test statistic, which follows a normal distribution; p is the p-value, the probability that measures the evidence against the null hypothesis; and Φ represents the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the standard normal distribution. The value of Z indicates the strength and direction of the trend. If Z is positive and significant, there is an increasing trend. If negative and significant, there is a decreasing trend.

We used the CMK test, an enhanced version of the traditional MK test, to assess the statistical significance of trends in the seasonality parameters (Neeti and Eastman, 2011). Unlike the original MK test (Kendall, 1975; Mann, 1945), the CMK test sequentially incorporates contextual information from first-order eight neighbours to account for spatial correlation, while correcting for cross-correlation. This extension is not part of the original STA framework (Eastman et al., 2009) but is incorporated here to improve the robustness of the trend significance assessment. The equations used to estimate CMK significance are given in Equations (S15)–(S17):

$$Z_m = \frac{\bar{S}_m - E(\bar{S}_m)}{\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{m}}} \quad (\text{S15})$$

$$\bar{S}_m = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m S_j \quad (\text{S16})$$

$$\text{Var}(\bar{S}_m) = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5)}{18m} = \frac{\sigma^2}{m} \quad (\text{S17})$$

where:

S_j is Kendall's for the j -th neighbour; $m = 9$ pixels, which includes eight neighbours with the central pixel; and $E(S)$ and σ are the mean (expected value) and standard deviation.

Adjustment for cross-correlation is done by introducing a covariance term in the calculation of variance (Equation S18):

$$Var(\bar{S}_m) = \frac{1}{m^2} \left[\sum_{j=1}^m Var(S_j) + 2 \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{l=1}^{m-j} Cov(S_j, S_{j+l}) \right] \quad (S18)$$

Unlike the Regionally Averaged Mann–Kendall (RAMK) approach proposed by Douglas et al. (2000), which primarily relies on regional aggregation, the CMK framework explicitly incorporates local spatial covariance among neighbouring pixels into the variance estimation procedure. According to Neeti and Ronald Eastman (2014), the CMK method reduces the detection of spurious trends while increasing confidence in the presence of consistent ones. Furthermore, the application of the TS slope offers the distinct advantage of filtering out interannual variability shorter than 0.29 times the series length. Together, these techniques are non-parametric and robust against the influence of outliers.

S2.3. False Discovery Rate (FDR) Control

We adjusted the p -values from the CMK test to account for multiple testing by controlling the false discovery rate (FDR) using the BH procedure (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995). This step is not included in the original STA framework and accounts for multiple testing, thereby limiting the inflation of Type I error associated with large numbers of simultaneous pixel-wise trend tests.

The FDR control procedure aims to control the proportion of spurious significances (false discoveries) relative to the total number of discoveries (i.e., the total number of tests declared significant) in a multiple-testing context (Benjamini, 2010).

Benjamini and Hochberg (BH) introduced the original FDR approach, which is the expected proportion of false discoveries within all discoveries (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995).

The FDR is formally defined as (Equation S19):

$$\text{FDR} = E \left[\frac{V}{R} \right] \quad (\text{S19})$$

where:

E denotes the expected value; V is the number of false positives (false discoveries); R is the total number of rejected hypotheses (discoveries).

The FDR-BH procedure is applied as follows:

1. Order the p -values of all the hypothesis tests in ascending order (Equation S20):

$$p_{(1)}, p_{(2)}, \dots, p_{(m)} \quad (\text{S20})$$

where:

$p_{(1)}$ represents the smallest p -value from the set of hypothesis tests; $p_{(2)}$ represents the second smallest p -value; $p_{(m)}$ represents the largest p -value; and m is the total number of hypothesis tests performed.

2. Determine the critical value k as the largest i such that (Equation S21):

$$p_{(i)} \leq \frac{i}{m} \cdot q \quad (\text{S21})$$

where:

$p_{(i)}$ denotes the p -value with rank i in the ordered set of hypothesis tests; i is the rank of the p -value when ordered from smallest to largest; m is the total number of hypothesis tests being performed; q is the desired FDR level, which plays the role of the significance threshold (i.e., the analogue of α in family-wise error control).

3. Reject all null hypotheses (Equation S22):

$$H_{(1)}, H_{(2)}, \dots, H_{(k)} \quad (\text{S22})$$

where:

$H_{(1)}$ represents the hypothesis corresponding to the smallest p -value; $H_{(2)}$ represents the hypothesis corresponding to the second smallest p -value; $H_{(k)}$ represents the hypothesis corresponding to the k -smallest p -value; and, k is the largest rank for which the p -value meets the FDR-BH criterion.

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